

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: This thesis describes factors that develop creativity, creative competence of pedagogic personnel, innovative activities of students, interactive education, innovative education and information and communication technologies, and students' creative abilities.

Key words: students, creativity, ability, interactive methods, innovation, education.

Introduction:

To increase the quality level of personnel training in Uzbekistan, to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists based on international standards, to establish close cooperation relations between each higher education institution and the leading scientific and educational institutions of the world, to the educational process Wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational materials based on international educational standards, effective use of interactive methods in the development of modern professional knowledge and creative abilities of students, scientific-pedagogical personnel is one of the urgent issues.

About this, in the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, priority tasks such as "*further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the possibilities of quality educational services, supporting and realizing the creative and intellectual potential of the young generation*" specified. Accordingly, it is important to develop students' creative abilities based on interactive teaching methods.

Today, one of the main tasks is to create a modern methodical support for the design of the creative education process by developing the creative competence of the pedagogic personnel, and to develop the creative abilities of students directed to the fields of professional activity. Creativity includes the organization of the educational process, the construction of a creative

educational process, the development of creative potential from educational technologies, the development of a balance of different methods, knowledge and skills.

Creativity is manifested as a set of skills related to creativity and creative qualities of a person. Creativity includes a high level of sensitivity to problems, intuition, foresight, imagination, research and reflection. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental sharpness. It can be seen that creativity is a process directly related to the individual-psychological characteristics of a person. Its development is influenced by the process of intellect-intuition-logical thinking.

In our country, as a result of consistent reforms aimed at creating conditions for a person, his all-round development and well-being, the realization of his interests, bringing the quality and efficiency of education to a new level, opportunities for the development of creative abilities of students are being created on the basis of interactive teaching methods. The term creativity appeared in Anglo-American psychology in the 60s. It means the ability and quality of an individual to create new concepts and new skills. American scientist J. Gilford shows a number of individual abilities that characterize creativity:

- *fluency of thought;*
- *ability to direct thoughts according to purpose;*
- *uniqueness (originality);*
- *curiosity;*
- *the ability to create hypotheses;*
- *imagination, fantasy (fantasy).*

The most important component in the structure of students' innovative activity is reflection. In order to fully understand the general nature of the process of developing creative qualities in a person, it is necessary to first understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity". The concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows: Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) is the creative ability of an individual that describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor.

A.H. Maslow divides creativity into two types: creativity of talent and creativity of individual self-actualization. Since creativity of self-actualization of a person is inextricably linked with a person, we can encounter it in everyday

life and in many areas of professional activity. H. Maslow mentioned two levels of self-actualization in creativity: the first - *"involuntary creativity, in which a person suddenly comes to his senses, inspiration, has difficult experiences"*, *"the second - voluntary, difficult related to work, continuous education, striving for perfection"*.

The analysis of the literature shows that the creative potential of a person is an independent view of the problem, contradictions, critical thinking; ability to analyze any problems, analytical thinking; the ability to find solutions for them; the possibility of transferring knowledge, skills and teaching methods to a new state; it can be manifested in skills such as the ability to combine previously learned methods with new ones.

Modern technologies teach the student to search for the acquired knowledge by himself, to study and analyze independently, and to draw conclusions by himself. Helping students to perform independent, creative activities means creating conditions for them to determine their positions and implement them in practice, providing tasks aimed at pedagogical support of their creative activities.

In interactive education, the teacher is an active organizer of educational activities, and the student appears as the subject of this activity. In this case, the goals and objectives of training, its content and expected results are determined directly within the individual capabilities of the learner and adjusted accordingly. Interactive teaching methods are an important means of implementing interactive education. Interactive methods are methods that serve to organize students' interaction and cooperation with the teacher in order to acquire knowledge, skills, competences and certain moral qualities.

The essence of interactive methods is to increase the student's activity in the teaching process, to make the student the central figure of the pedagogical activity. To activate the students, the correct choice of the methods used in the course of the lesson and the precise formulation of the questions will have a great effect. For this purpose, the goal of the subject should be clearly defined in the lesson, and the way and method of achieving this goal should be carefully considered. The teacher should be able to foresee what each of the interactive methods used will give to the student and organize the lesson correctly.

Interactive education is organized on the basis of the possibility of cooperation, intense debates, exchange of ideas between the main participants of the teaching process - the teacher, student and student group, in which they can think freely, express their personal views. to express without hesitation, to

search for solutions in problem situations together, to create mutual closeness of students in mastering educational materials, mutual respect, understanding and support of the "teacher-student-student group" -characterized by their support, sincere relationship, and the achievement of spiritual unity.

With the help of interactive education, the teacher develops students' abilities, independence, self-control, self-management, effective conversation, working with peers, listening and understanding their opinions, independent, creative, will be able to form such qualities as critical thinking, putting forward alternative proposals, expressing opinions freely, defending one's point of view, striving to find a solution to a problem, and being able to get out of difficult situations. Most importantly, through the use of interactive educational technologies, the teacher provides the possibility of objective evaluation by organizing, directing, directing, controlling and analyzing the actions of students based on mutual cooperation in order to achieve a specific educational goal. enters into

Interactive educational methods and technologies are of particular importance in the formation of students' creative abilities. Therefore, there is a need to determine the specific content, tools, pedagogical conditions, features and methods of the interactive teaching process aimed at developing creativity. Based on interactive teaching methods, we found it appropriate to carry out the following work on the problems of developing students' creative abilities:

- *organization of trainings that serve to develop students' skills of data analysis, quick decision-making, and creative thinking;*
- *performing creative exercises and assignments aimed at forming imaginations and imaginative views; working with cases;*
- *organization of group work forms and debates; preparation of educational projects; formation of portfolios; establishing the activities of clubs.*
- *performing creative tasks;*
- *work in small groups;*
- *trainings;*
- *video trainings;*
- *presentations;*
- *quizzes;*
- *creative design training;*
- *interactive tours;*
- *interactive lectures;*
- *webinar;*

- *roundtable discussions.*

To do this, it is necessary to create a free-creative environment that serves to develop students' creative abilities, to establish a teaching process based on mutual relations and cooperative actions of professors, teachers, teachers and students.

So, creativity is manifested as a set of skills related to creativity and creative qualities of a person. Creativity includes a high level of sensitivity to problems, intuition, foresight, imagination, research and reflection.

Analysis and results:

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental sharpness.

Also, creativity of a person depends on pedagogical competence. Regarding this, research scientist L.M. Mitina describes pedagogical competence as follows:

- *active (knowledge, skills, professional skills and individual methods of responsible and independent implementation of pedagogical activities);*
- *communicative (creative ways of implementing pedagogical communication);*
- *personal (work on yourself, self-development skills).*

In our country, the research conducted by B. Nazarova on the professional competence of a pedagogue and its specific aspects is of special importance. According to the researcher, the professional competence of a pedagogue is based on the following structural foundations:

- *special or professional competence (organization of professional activity at a high level);*
- *social competence (collaborative organization of professional competence, social responsibility);*
- *auto-competence (ability to develop oneself socially and professionally);*
- *extreme professional competence, that is, the ability to take the right course in unexpected situations.*

On the one hand, professional competence is an integral criterion of professional training and the quality of professional activity, on the other hand, it is a property of a person characterized by highly qualified worker functions, work culture and interpersonal communication, initiative skills and creative solving of professional problems.

A person's creativity is evidenced by his personality, work experience, civil status, position as a specialist, sufficient mastery of pedagogical techniques, individuality of professional activity. One of the factors affecting the quality of training students at the level of modern requirements is professional competence and creativity. This includes a holistic conceptual approach to the profession (a clear idea of how and what to teach), the ability to appreciate work (*motivation to teach*), optimization of the educational process, self-management, self-development requires training such characteristics as working on oneself.

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental sharpness. It can be seen that creativity is a process directly related to the individual-psychological characteristics of a person. Its development is influenced by the process of intellect-intuition-logical thinking.

The development of creativity in students requires the proper organization of the teaching process, depending on the level of knowledge, the level of mastery, the source of education, and didactic tasks of students in mastering the educational content. It is assumed that the following pedagogical conditions must be followed:

- *to determine students' inclinations to acquire creative activity, to form knowledge needs and to provide an environment for the manifestation of independence in the educational process;*
- *to create a comfortable opportunity for students to think creatively, to accept various opinions and ideas expressed by students with tolerance and to ensure their activity in the educational process, to establish confidence in each student's ability to think creatively, regular stimulation of their creative activities;*
- *individualization of the educational process based on the characteristics, needs and intellectual potential of the student;*
- *formation of students' individual, small group and team work skills, expanding their creative capabilities, encouraging them to accept non-standard solutions along with ready, standard solutions in solving problems;*
- *selection and implementation of interactive training forms and methods that allow re-development and improvement of cognitive knowledge, which is the basis of the development of creative activity.*

Pedagogical creativity is the ability of a pedagogue to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as well as to positively solve existing pedagogical problems, in contrast to traditional pedagogical thinking, and it is necessary to guarantee the following two conditions:

1) *attracting the attention of students who have low mastery of academic subjects and who consider their study boring by teachers to master the basics of science;*

2) *to create an opportunity for teachers to use them effectively in the audience by recommending strategies and tools that serve to stimulate creative thinking and creative activity results in students.*

So, creativity is manifested as a set of skills related to creativity and creative qualities of a person. Creativity includes a high level of sensitivity to problems, intuition, foresight, imagination, research and reflection. It is necessary to systematically study the pedagogical needs, interests, directions of special importance of the students, in which it is necessary to define effective ways to eliminate the psychological obstacles encountered in the organization of creative activities.

The organization of the teaching process based on ideas, concepts and advanced pedagogical experiences that serve to satisfy the creative interests and needs of students serves to form a meaningful and active approach to the development of creativity. Based on the development of students' creativity skills, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the development of their specialized, i.e., pedagogical creativity competence, in which it is appropriate to widely use modern information and communication technologies, innovative strategies, interactive educational methods and technologies. Improving educational programs and technologies aimed at the continuous development of students' creative competence of educational institutions, as well as creating modern information-methodical support that serves to develop the creative abilities of students, serves to increase the efficiency of the process.

Conclusion:

In short, interactive educational methods and technologies are of particular importance in the formation of students' creative abilities, and the interactive teaching process aimed at developing creativity in them has its own content, tools, pedagogical conditions, features and methods. must be Development of creative educational programs that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the reproductive, creative-research and innovation stages of the development of

students' creative abilities in higher education institutions, and to evaluate the changes in the development of creative skills and skills of students.

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